

TYPES OF SYNTACTIC RELATION

Holikulova Gulchekhira Yorkulovna

Eshboyeva Oysanam Sokhatmuratovna

Teachers of the Department of Uzbek Language and Literature,
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8069858>

Abstract: In the article, the types of syntactic relations studied in Uzbek linguistics were highlighted. Also, predicative relationship, object relationship, case relationship, connecting means of subordinate words in attributive relationships and the formation of syntactic relationship were studied with the help of examples.

Key words: syntactic relationship, syntactic relationship, word combination, predicative relationship, object relationship, case relationship, attributive relationship, possessive, participle, complement, determiner.

Annotation : V state vydeleny tipy syntaxischeskih atnosheniy, izuchaemye v Uzbekskom zazykoznanii. Krome togo, na primerax izuchalis predicativnye atnosheniy, obektnye atnoshenye, dedejnye atnosheniy, sredstva soedineniya pridatochnyx slov v attributivnyx atnoshenyakh i obrazovanie syntaxischeskih atnosheniy.

Key words: syntactic connection, slovosochetanie, predicativnaya connection, object connection, case connection, attributivnaya connection, prityajatelnoe, prichastie, popolnenie, opredelitel.

Annotation: The article highlights the types of syntactic relations studied in Uzbek linguistics. In addition, examples were used to study predicative relations, object relations, case relations, means of connecting subordinate words in attributive relations, and the formation of syntactic relations.

Key words: syntactic link, phrase, predicative link, object link, case link, attributive link, possessive, participle, object, determiner.

From the syntax department of Uzbek linguistics, the interrelationship of words is interpreted between phrases and sentences. We can recognize several scientists not only in Uzbek and Russian linguistics.

The work done by FFFortunatov, AMPeshkovskiy, VVVinogradov, NNProkopovich, VVBurlakova, NIFilicheva, AAREformatsky and other scientists is exemplary in the study of word combinations in Russian linguistics. In Turkish linguistics, the issues of word formation were thoroughly studied in the research works of scientists such as A.N.¹

When thinking about the types of syntactic relations between word combinations in Uzbek linguistics, we should distinguish syntactic relations from syntactic relations. In some literature, there are cases where these two concepts are used interchangeably. The concept of syntactic relation is formed using syntactic relations.

are expressed about syntactic relations and syntactic relations and their types: they use it interchangeably, synonymously. As a result, it is concluded that both these terms reflect the

¹ Shodiyev SE Syntactic derivation of fixed word combinations// Dissertation of Doctor of Philosophy in Philology, - Samarkand, 2020, page 5

same thing. True, syntactic connection and syntactic relationship are related to each other: where there is syntactic relationship, there is also syntactic relationship. But this does not allow them to be evaluated as the same thing. Any syntactic relation is different from syntactic relationship.

The syntactic relationship indicates the grammatical meaning and function of the words in free phrases and sentences, as well as sentences in speech. Syntactic connection means the grammatical connection of the words in the phrase and the sentence and the sentences in the speech.

BO'rinboev in the textbook "Syntactic relations in the current Uzbek literary language": "Syntactic relations are expressed using syntactic relations. Although syntactic relationship and syntactic relationship are two sides of the same phenomenon that require each other, but both of them do not necessarily correspond to each other due to the fact that they have certain characteristics. For example, vocative and modal relations, which are part of syntactic relation, are not part of syntactic relationship.

Based on the above points, we will pay attention to the grammatical means connecting subordinate and dominant parts in syntactic communication, mainly in the example of word combinations. For example, we will see in the example of the agreement between the subordinate and the ruler parts: he went to the library, he went to the institute, and we will analyze it under the examples of his brother, he looked after his sister. Here, in all word combinations, the subject and the governing part are connected by the conjunction of departure. Analyzing the syntactic relation, in the combination he went to the library and to the institute, he is performing the function of case to the library, to the institute, and in the combination he took to his brother, he looked to his sister, he is performing the function of complement to his brother, to his sister. So, although the syntactic relation is expressed by the same form, it performs two different functions in the syntactic relation: complement and case function.

The following are the most important relationships between syntactically related words:

1. Predicative relationship. In this case, the word in the possessive function enters into a syntactic relationship with the word in the participle function. For example, we went, students came, I saw, he listened, etc.

2. Object relation. In this case, the word in the function of a filler comes into contact with the word. Complements and complements are syntactically connected with the help of infinitives, departures, place-times, exit clauses, and auxiliaries. For example, read a book, call him, write in a notebook, tell his mother, ask a friend, get it for his child... In the object relation, the means of connecting the subordinate and dominant words are different, but the same. a syntactic relationship is emerging.

3. Holly attitude. In this case, the word in the function of the case comes into contact with the word in the function of declension. For example, to skip class, to go out, to go in the summer... Holly relation has the same connecting means as object relation, but the syntactic relation is different.

4. Attributive relation. In this case, the defining word and the defined word come into contact. For example, blue sky, fresh air, blue-blue field, my yard, our classroom... In the attributive relationship, the means of connecting subordinate and dominant words are tone and demonstrative agreement. Although the linking device is not the same, the same type of

syntactic relationship is occurring.

It should be said that in some cases the means of connecting subordinate and dominant parts change the above types of relations. For example, the auxiliary with mainly creates an object relationship: to come with his brother, to go by car... there are cases when these tools also serve to create an objective relationship: to study diligently, with pleasure like to sing.

Types of syntactic relations were analyzed on the example of free word combinations. So, when determining the type of syntactic relations, we must take into account the necessary factors that we pay attention to, along with the tools that bring words into communication, as well as the lexical-semantic features of the communicating elements. We should pay attention to the syntactic relationship in order not to create different types of syntactic relations between subordinate and dominant words depending on the connecting means.

References:

- 1.Orinboyev B., Problems of Uzbek colloquial speech syntax. - Tashkent: "Fan", 1974.
- 2.Ghulomov A., Askarova M. Modern Uzbek literary language. Syntax. - Tashkent, 1987.
- 3.Berdialiyev A. Syntactic connection and syntactic relations in Uzbek adverbial clauses. - Tashkent, 1992.
- 4.Mahmudov N., Nurmonov A. Theoretical grammar of the Uzbek language.-Tashkent, 1995, p. 21.
- 5.Orinboyev B., Lectures on the phraseology and syntax of the modern Uzbek literary language. - Tashkent, 1990, page 86.
- 6.Nurmonov A. And others. Meaningful syntax of the Uzbek language. -Tashkent, 1992, page 94.
- 7.Mahmudov N., Nurmonov A. and others. Meaningful syntax of the Uzbek language. - Tashkent, 1992.
- 8.Shodiyev S. Syntactic derivation of Turgun word combinations// Doctor of Philosophy Diss. in Philology, - Samarkand, 2020, 125 pages.